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TRAFFIC DISSECTOR: DISCOVER AND INSPECT YOUR NETWORK

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Abstract

A network generally consists of number of devices connected to each other. It is necessary that the team of networking people or the network administrators should have complete information about the network and its topology. In order to find out the devices and the topology of the network the network administrators have to run several show commands on the device and have to log in into several other devices and repeat the same to find out the exact topology of the network which leads to wastage of a lot of time.

In this research paper we discuss an application that is developed to provide complete network topology information to aid network engineers who want to discover the underlying network topology, flow of traffic and the type of data that is sent on the network. The application developed is interactive, easy to use and dynamically displays the change in traffic as well.

Keywords- SDN; Network Discovery; Traffic Inspection; Link Utilization; Packet Drop Count; OnePK API ; Utilization Graphs

Introduction

Today's traditional network architectures are not developed enough or are not flexible enough to meet the variably scalable requirements of enterprises, carriers and end users. To meet these highly variable requirements the concept of SDN was developed. Software Defined Networking commonly known as SDN is among the hot trending concepts today in the networking industry. In SDN the control and the data planes are decoupled and act as separate entities. All the network intelligence and state is logically centralized. Thus it serves as the abstraction for other features and programs to be developed over it.

Earlier the introduction of the x86 architecture brought abstraction in the world of computers allowing us to choose the operating system for our machines, thereby, making it flexible. Similarly in the world of networking SDN is going to provide same abstraction on the networking devices.

This application is built keeping in mind the concepts of SDN such that it will be able to discover the network devices that work on layer 3 and plot the network topology on the screen. The user with the help of interface will be able to click on any link and get the details of the traffic flowing through it.

The traffic details that will be shown include the transmit and the receive rate of the packets through that link and packet drops. In case the packets starts dropping due to congestion in the link it can be easily determined with the help of this feature. There is another feature of graph that shows the link utilization in the terms of packet count which will be plotted on the per protocol basis. Every protocol will be having its own separate colored line to identify it uniquely.

Related Works

Common network discovery techniques

ICMP Ping: It is the most common way to discover the hosts on the network which uses the ICMP Echo request which the target hosts reply with ICMP Echo reply messages. **TCP SYN Ping:** The host existence can be learned from either open or closed TCP ports, one can increase the reliability of the scan by targeting a frequently opened port 80 and a frequently closed port 0.

TCP ACK Ping: ACK Ping works almost like the above SYN Ping, with the exception that it relies on an ACK packet instead. This method works by soliciting a RST response from a live host for either open or closed ports by sending it an ACK packet.

TCP FIN, NULL, Xmas Ping: FIN, NULL and Xmas Pings work by generating a RST response for a closed port. Such pings must be sent to a known closed port to produce a reply such as port 0.

UDP Ping: UDP Ping works by producing an ICMP port unreachable error when attempting to communicate with a closed UDP port. Once again we will be using port 0.

ARP Ping: ARP Ping is a preferred host discovery method on a local Ethernet LAN, because it is faster and more reliable than approaches relying on protocols higher up in the networking stack. It works by sending ARP Probes to a range of IP addresses to discover live hosts.

IP Protocol Ping: This method attempts to solicit a host reply by sending raw IP packets with varying protocol id options.

Common network discovery applications: Nmap, Angry IP scanner etc...

The very first thing for the network discovery tools like nmap is we have to specify the network range in which we want to discover the devices. So the discovery that happens is limited to that particular network range. In that case, let's say, we have a real variable range of IP's into our organization's network with IP's in all the three classes namely A,B and C. In that case these network tools take large amount of time to discover the network devices.

Nmap usually works on the concept of ping. It tries to ping every given IP address in the given subnet range to check if the hosts are alive or not. But this method is not always reliable because some network devices have the shield of firewall blocking these pings. Windows firewall blocks ping by default. The other commonly available network discovery tools also work in the similar way.

Proposed Model

General System Design

The Traffic Dissector system is composed of a front end and a back end. The front end part will be consisting of the GUI application with which the user can interact. The front end will deal with the following functions:

Discovering Topology:

The traffic dissector application establishes a connection to the network elements and discovers the topology iteratively. The purpose is to dynamically discover and display the topology on the GUI.

Displaying Topology:

All the connected links between the routers will be labeled with the interface numbers and interfaces will be colored as green and red when they are active and inactive respectively. Mouse over the links and routers will display its network properties like hostname of the router, IP address, interface IP addresses etc.

Traffic Inspection on link:

We can inspect different types of traffic that is flowing through that link. It provides the following functionalities:

- Transmit Rate of packets flowing
- Receive Rate of packets flowing
- Packet Drops
- List of all protocols flowing through that link with:
 - ✓ Protocol Name
 - ✓ Link Utilization of every protocol (Packet Count)
 - ✓ Graph plotted for every protocol in terms of packet count vs present/previous time scale on which the system is running.

The other part of the system i.e. the back end will have the use of OnePK API to retrieve the necessary data from the topology such as link status, type of traffic, Rate of certain type of traffic, list of links that are operational for a device.

Cisco OnePK

The application is developed using an SDK called ONE (Open Networking Environment) Programmability Kit (OnePK). OnePK is a cross platform API and software development kit that enables users to develop applications that interact directly with Cisco networking devices, and provides them with the ability to access networking services using a set of controlled APIs that share the same programming model and style.

One PK, which has an extensive C/Java APIs set, allows users to develop an application that interacts with a node in the network and can get or set the state of the system. For this project, we have used the JAVA and C SDK that are available. The figure below shows how the One PK infrastructure lies above any OS of the device and shows the output of the application using C or JAVA.

Figure 1: onePK Architecture

Technical Feasibility/ Constraints

For the required system to work some features need to be ensured.

The routers should run an OS version that supports ONE-PK API sets and allow for application sessions to run on the box. The IP address of the base device (root node / router) need to be known, along with its login credentials – Username and Password. The application runs on a limited number of routers

Sequence Diagrams

The discovery module will be triggered when the user enters the correct IP, username and password for the base router. From then onwards the topology will be recursively discovered.

Figure 2: Discovery module

The discovery module will present the user with an interactive topology diagram. When the user clicks on a link in the diagram, a pop-up will show displaying link statistics.

Figure 3: Link Statistics Module

The pop-up for link statistics will also contain a button, clicking which will invoke a live graph that will display protocol-wise link utilization (display packet counts on Y-axis)

Figure 4: Protocol-wise utilization module

System Design Screenshots

Figure 5: User input Pop-up

Figure 6: Step by step Topology Discovery

Figure 7: Fully Discovered Topology

Figure 8: Link Statistics pop-up when link is clicked

Figure 9: ‘Display Graph’ displays a Protocol wise line chart

Conclusion

To conclude, the application fulfills three requirements. It dynamically discovers any given topology and displays the topology on the UI for the TAC (Technical assistance Centre) engineer to view. The network engineer may click on any of the links and inspect traffic on these links. The values are updated according to traffic flowing through the links. It is able to show for important values- Transmit rate, receive Rate, Input drops and output drops. The display graph option shows the per protocol flow through given links. The graph shows instantaneous values and updates every 5 seconds. Each of the protocol flow is represented by a different color on the graph. It has a proper UI that makes it easy for the user to operate the systems. These functionalities make the job of the TAC engineer faster. Instead of manually typing commands to view this information, the TAC engineer is able to get the view of the topology with just a few clicks.

Results

We performed some basic tests that allowed us to validate the functionalities provided by the application. These tests include generating ICMP and Telnet Traffic to see if expected values are displayed on interface statistics pop-up and protocol graph.


```
changed state to up
NE102#
NE102#
NE102#
NE102#ping 10.34.1.4 repeat 10
Type escape sequence to abort.
Sending 10, 100-byte ICMP Echos to 10.34.1.4, timeout is 2 seconds:
!!!!!!
Success rate is 100 percent (10/10), round-trip min/avg/max = 1/3/13 ms
NE102#telnet
```

Figure 13: Ping Traffic

```
NE102#telnet 10.34.1.4
Trying 10.34.1.4 ... Open

Password required, but none set

[Connection to 10.34.1.4 closed by foreign host]
```

Figure 14: Telnet Traffic

Figure 15: Telnet, Ping and the total utilization

The graph represents different protocols flows using different colors on the same graph. This gives us an idea of the number of packets for each of the protocols at that instant.

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